

Illusion of "Value Added" in Indian Industry

Sourish Dutta

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ABSTRACT

According to ASI database, although the flow of "Net Income" is increasing impressively, the flow of intensity of net income (i.e. net income/output) is in decline mode. Through acute statistical analysis, throughout ASI data, it is noted that the fluctuating behaviour of net income time series is fully characterised by profit flow, while the falling trend is imposed by emolument flow. The problem is all about lack of synchronicity between flows of net income and its share to total output. In immediate response, it can be said that the growth of net income, to some extent, is statistical illusion. Now the obvious questions are: what are the influencing factors behind the decline of net income intensity? Is there any latent factor? What would be its consequence? In this paper, we will address all these issues at aggregate level as well as at disaggregated level of ASI database.

I feel (after reading ASI manual) that "Net Income" reflects pure value added rather than GVA or NVA. Because, net income is derived from after adjust the net rent/interest paid for production. That's why here I have used "Net Income" as a proper indicator of value addition.

I. Brief Introduction

Apparently, though the paper's title is indicating about criticism of statistical artifact, it is purely about examining hidden mechanisms of the flow of value added in Indian industry. For this analysis, here we will rely only on ASI database. The idea is derived indirectly from the debate of manufacturing growth in the new GDP series. However, if we plot the net income time series, we would see a clear and upward trend (with impressive growth) with time. But the problem is: the rising fact of net income is not consistent with its intensity. The figure 1 (below) is showing the time series of both variables from 1981 to 2012. Here r2 is the intensity of net income.

Figure 1. Flow of Net Income and its share to Output (intensity)

In the figure above, it is noted that there are three different downfalls of share of net income to output viz. in 1980s (from first half onwards), second half of 1990s and late 2000s. The average extent of these downfalls, more or less, are equivalent. As we are in 21st century, we are comparatively more concerned about the fall of late 2000s. This fall started from 2007 with decline of above 15% to above 11%. After studying the previous two downfalls, the current downfall might touch a new record low-level share of net income in Indian industry. In fact, the flow of intensity had touched a record low-level around 10% of total output. As a result, we can see a flat region in

the absolute flow of net income in neighbourhood of the year 2000.

II. Decomposition (Direct)

To examine the downfall of net income intensity, we will decompose the net income into total emolument and profits. In figure 2, r3 is profit intensity and r4 is emolument intensity.

Figure 2. Decomposition of Net Income Intensity

In this figure, we are getting some interesting facts. Though both factors are very much influential to net income, emolument intensity was dominant factor (trend determining) to aggregate. After 2002, the profit intensity had become the leading factor to net income. However, from overall view, we can feel that the profit intensity was always shape/fluctuation determining factor, whereas emolument intensity was trend determining component. Besides this, there is a tendency of declining gap between share of profit and emolument at aggregate. Indeed, the 21st century's decline in share of net income can be explained directly through profit intensity. Here we can imagine a criss-cross/oscillatory relationship between share of profit and share of emolument, which can be predicted through classical political economy, and it is happened due to lack of indigenous innovative capacity or technological progress. But the influence of technological progress, to some extent, latent or invisible. In order to show the effect of technology, we should go to the root of net income. Therefore, we need to show the derivation of value added at gross level from total output.

III. Decomposition (Indirect)

Origin of net income is gross value added and the origin of gross value added is gross value of output. In simple form, gross value of output is divided into two parts, one is total input and second is gross value added. In this paper we are interested in share/intensity to total output. Therefore, we want to depict input intensity as well as value added intensity. Here r_6 is indicated for input intensity, whereas r_7 is indicated for gross value added intensity.

Figure 3. Flows of Input and Net Value Added Intensities

In latest data, it is noted that contribution of total input to output is about 83%, while 17% of output is contributed by gross value added. We know that the sum of these two intensities is equal to 1. Therefore, if input intensity is rising, then obviously intensity of gross value added would fall. Through econometric test it is also established that there is a short run as well as long run perfect negative relationship between two factors of total output. Hence, the explanation of downfall in the share of value added can be made through rising share of input to output, and this rising trend of input intensity can be properly explained through the issues of productive efficiency of Indian industry. My claim is: there are some latent or hidden parameters which are influencing inputs but not value added, and finally the value added intensity is affected by influenced input intensity. Indeed, productive efficiency is true reflection of existing indigenous innovative capacity

or real technological prosperity in production process.

Now if we decompose the input intensity into material and fuel consumed, we will see that the contribution of material intensity is higher than fuel, and it is rising year by year. Actually, total input comprises gross value of fuel materials etc. consumed and also other inputs viz. (a) cost of non-industrial services received from others (b) cost of materials consumed for repair and maintenance of factory's fixed assets including cost of work done by others to the factory's fixed assets (c) cost of contract and commission work done by others on materials supplied by the factory (d) cost of office supplies and products reported for sale during last year & used for further manufacture during the accounting year. But due to limitation of the aggregate database, we will confine ourselves within two factors. In the figure 4, r8 is representing fuel intensity, whereas r9 is representing material intensity.

Figure 4. Decomposition of Input Intensity into Fuel and Material Consumed

In this figure, the interesting fact is: over the period the Indian industry had become fuel efficient, because fuel intensity curve (overall) is falling with a slight increase in recent years. However, we can derive the partial productivity of inputs through dividing the total output to total input. Similarly, we can also find the fuel intensity as well as material intensity. In the figure 5, r10 is representing total input productivity, r11 is for fuel productivity, and r12 is for material productivity. Out of all inputs, indeed, only fuel productivity is in the rising trend. These productivity issues can be related easily with the applied technological capacity. After all production function is true indication of prevailing technological base.

Figure 5. Productivity of Inputs

Through this aggregate database we can capture some partial picture of technological condition of the industrial production process. It can be done by plotting time series of skilled productivity and unskilled productivity. Skilled productivity can be calculated through dividing total output by skilled wages and similar case for unskilled one also. Here skilled wages can be found by subtracting wages to workers, Bonus and other welfare payments from the total emolument. In the figure 6, bias skill is meant by ratio of skilled wages to unskilled wages. Along the the time line, though the productivity gap between skilled and unskilled workers has gone down, the index of skill bias is still increasing. Truly, reliance on skilled workers is increasing year by year. But if we cross check this skilled bias trend by the ratio of number of skilled workers to unskilled workers (figure 7), it indicates that currently payments per skilled worker is much higher than the previous case.

On the other hand, the technological issue can also be reflected through capital-labour ratio in the Indian industry. Here (figure 8) we have calculated different capital-labour ratios. $KL(E)$ ratios for invested capital to labour (employees), whereas $KbyL(E)$ ratios are meant for physical working capital to labour(employees) in the production process. All ratios are rising except $KbyE$ ratio. Here L is for workers and E is for all employees. I think the valid ratios are KL and $KbyL$, and both are rising as time flows. The overall picture of production process and its environment can be reflected through the rate of net investment (figure 9). Indeed, the picture is not much impressive, and its flow is in negative growth (statistically significant) throughout the period of study. It also depicts the present crisis of business confidence and innovative capacity.

Figure 6. Skill-Biased Production Process

Figure 7. Ratio of number of skilled workers to unskilled

Figure 8. Capital Labour Ratios

Figure 9. Net Investment Rate

IV. Mapping of Sectors

In order to verify those above interesting facts at disaggregated level of Indian industry, we will use a unique type of mapping at 2-digit level in ASI database. In this mapping, we are interested about two types of sectors viz. one is Good Sector and another is Bad Sector. Here "Good" ("Bad") one is defined as higher net income intensity as well as higher growth rate of net income intensity from aggregate average and vice-versa. But here we have focused only on manufacturing sectors.

Decade	High	Low
1970s	17,22,26,28,29,33,34,35	15,19,23,24,25,27
1980s	16,31	17,19,20,24,25
1990s	16,18,24,33,36	15,17,21,28,30,32
2000s	26,30,31	19,20,25,28,32,36

Note: High (Low) = Higher NII, G_NII (Lower) than Aggregate Average.

If we analyse these scheduled good sectors, we will find that the driving factor of their 'high' nature is majorly due to higher profit intensity not the emolument intensity (same at aggregate level). We have presented these in the figures below. Though the fluctuation in profit intensity is much more than emolument intensity, it has clear rising trend. And if we see the flow of net income intensities of these sectors, then we can properly feel that the fluctuating behaviour is totally driven by profit, while the declining trend is characterised by emolument. See the figure 11 and match it with figure 10.

Figure 10. Profit and Emolument Intensities of 'Good' Sectors

Therefore, here we have same type of realisation after mapping the pure good sectors. Now we have to see whether the share of these sectors to aggregate net income has grown up or not along time line. But the figure 12 is not indicating a good sign for Indian industry. Currently its share

Figure 11. Net Income Intensity of 'Good' Sectors

is around 12%. Meanwhile, the share of so called 'Bad' sectors (figure 13) to aggregate net income is also falling, and in recent past it was around 10%. Nevertheless, the overall picture is implying that there is a positive hope of raising the share of 'Good' sectors rather than 'bad' ones.

Figure 12. Share of 'Good' Sectors in Aggregate Net Income

Figure 13. Share of 'Bad' Sectors in Aggregate Net Income